

Introduction: The South Pole–Aitken (SPA) basin is the largest and oldest impact structure on the Moon. This highly energetic event likely excavated thought the crust and exposed mantle material on the lunar surface. Determining the trajectory of the SPA impact and distribution of its ejecta is therefore critical for identifying the locations of samples that anchor the early impact chronology and constrain models of mantle composition.

While it had generally been assumed that SPA ejecta contributed to the thickness of the far side crust, Garrick-Bethell et al. [4] suggested that the far side topography had formed before SPA, leaving the impact trajectory uncertain. Current debate centers on whether the basin formed by an oblique impact directed toward or away from the south pole. A trajectory away from the pole has been suggested on the basis of magnetic anomalies along the northern rim as potential downrange projectile-core deposits [13] and 3D hydrocode simulations [2,3]. In contrast, a poleward trajectory has been proposed based on massif distribution [11], and basin tapering morphology observed in gravity and topography data [1].

In this work, we focus on directly searching for a signature of SPA ejecta in Bouguer gravity data. Such a signal may be preserved if the ejecta possessed a significantly different porosity in comparison to the pre-SPA crust and the ejecta volume was large enough to induce partial crustal compensation. If it extended to depths accessible only to large impacts—less frequent than smaller ones—this subsurface layer may have avoided complete mixing and thus remain detectable as a subsurface porosity feature. Our null hypothesis is that no such signal is present in the Bouguer gravity data.

Methods: *Impact induced porosity boundaries from Residual Bouguer Anomaly (RBA) of craters.* The RBA is defined as the difference between the mean Bouguer anomaly within a crater and that of the surrounding terrain. Because excavation depth increases with crater diameter, variations in RBA as a function of crater size reflect changes in subsurface density. Assuming impact-induced porosity is the main driver of density changes with depth, slope breaks in RBA–diameter trends can indicate transitions between distinct porosity layers, while accounting for noise introduced by compositional heterogeneity unrelated to porosity. This method has previously been used to constrain the average depth of megaregolith layers in the lunar crust [6,10].

We investigate potential porosity boundaries in two candidate SPA ejecta regions, one located south and one north of SPA, corresponding to impact trajectories directed toward and away from the pole,

respectively. To assess the significance of any inferred porosity boundary, we define three control regions: one on the lunar far side, one on the near side, and one between the inner and outer rims of SPA, as defined in James et al. [8].

We analyze trends in the RBA of craters in each region. We use the global crater database of Robbins [9] and select craters with diameters between 5 and 30 km within each region while ignoring the ones located in mare regions. We use the topography-corrected Bouguer gravity data from the GRAIL mission [5] to compute the RBA of craters between 5 and 10 km, building on previously published RBA data sets of craters >10 km [6]. Finally, we fit a two-slope model to RBA data within diameters 5–30 km and find the depth of potential porosity boundaries associated to slope breaks.

Crater depth-to-diameter ratio. It has been previously proposed that craters formed in higher-porosity targets exhibit larger depth-to-diameter ratios than those formed in lower-porosity materials [14]. To evaluate whether the candidate ejecta regions display differences in mean target porosity— independent of the presence of discrete porosity boundaries—we compute the average depth-to-diameter ratio for craters within each ejecta and control region. We use the global crater depth values of Wang et al. [12].

Results and discussion: Figure 1 shows the inferred porosity boundaries. Within uncertainty, both candidate ejecta regions exhibit boundaries around 4 km in depth, consistent with the control regions and the previously published shallow global megaregolith structure. Owing to the use of an expanded crater database that includes craters smaller than 10 km in diameter, the inferred porosity boundary is better constrained than in previous studies, proposed to be between 3–5 km [6].

Based on these results, we cannot conclusively identify a distinct porosity signature associated with SPA ejecta. This outcome suggests several possibilities: the ejecta emplacement may have produced primarily a topographic feature without significant crustal compensation; any original porosity contrast may have been erased by billions of years of impact-driven mixing; or a porosity layer may exist at depths too shallow to be resolved with the currently available gravity data.

Craters within the candidate ejecta regions do not exhibit higher depth-to-diameter ratios compared to those in the control regions. Although this finding is consistent with the absence of a distinct SPA ejecta porosity signature, other factors may influence the results. For all but the freshest craters, the effects of degradation likely make it difficult to distinguish the

influence of target porosity. For example, craters in the lunar highlands do not display systematically higher depth-to-diameter ratios than craters in mare regions, despite the higher average porosity of the highlands [12].

Figure 1. Inferred depths of porosity boundaries for the candidate SPA ejecta and control regions. (a) Map of chosen regions. Dots show the location of craters used in this analysis. Colors show the best-fitting boundary depth for each region. Although some regions appear to exhibit distinct best-fitting depths, the differences are small and likely not significant relative to the noise introduced by compositional variations unrelated to porosity. (b) Inferred boundary depths with corresponding uncertainties derived from noise in the RBA data.

Future work: This work will be expanded by analyzing additional candidate ejecta regions, including butterfly-pattern deposits [3] and by applying complementary approaches to constrain subsurface density and porosity structures, such as estimating the effective crustal density in these regions [7]. A more detailed assessment of crater depth-to-diameter ratios is also warranted. In particular, examining pairs of craters of comparable size with well-constrained emplacement locations relative to ejecta deposits—possible at basins younger than SPA (e.g. Orientale)—

would help isolate ejecta-related effects. If systematic differences in depth-to-diameter ratios are observed in craters emplaced over ejecta deposits, compared to the ones outside of these deposits, applying this refined analysis to candidate SPA ejecta regions would be justified.

References: [1] Andrews-Hanna J. C. et al. (2025) *Nature*, 646, 297–302. [2] Bill C. A. et al. (2024) *LPSC*, Abstract #2007. [3] Citron R. I. et al. (2024) *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 51. [4] Garrick-Bethell I. et al. (2010) *Science*, 330, 949–951. [5] Goossens S. et al. (2020) *JGR Planets*, 125. [6] Izquierdo K. et al. (2021) *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 48. [7] Izquierdo K. et al. (2024) *JGR Planets*, 129. [8] James P. B. et al. (2019) *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 46, 5100–5106. [9] Robbins S. J. (2019) *JGR Planets*, 124, 871–892. [10] Soderblom J. M. et al. (2015) *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 42, 6939–6944. [11] Schultz P. H. and Crawford D. A. (2011) *Geol. Soc. Am. Spec. Pap.* 477, 141–159. [12] Wang Y. et al. (2021) *JGR Planets*, 126. [13] Wieczorek M. A. et al. (2012) *Science*, 335, 1212–1215. [14] Wünnemann K., Collins G. S., and Melosh H. J. (2006) *Icarus*, 180, 514–527.